

RELATIONS OF THE MESOSCOPIC DAMAGE MECHANISMS WITH THE MACROSCOPIC PROPERTIES OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

Chen Haoran¹ and Su Xiaofeng²

^{1,2} *State Key Laboratory of Structural Analysis of Industrial Equipments, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian, 116023, P. R. China.*

SUMMARY: Generalized self-consistent finite element iterative averaging method is united with the Gurson model for the parametric investigation of the damage mechanisms and their relations with the macroscopic tensile properties of the SiC reinforced Al₅₄₅₆. The mesoscopic damage mechanisms studied here contain two types: interphase debonding between the reinforcement and matrix and the nucleation, growth, and coalescence of the voids in the matrix. The interphase debonding could promote the nucleation and growth of the voids in matrix, which increases the ductility of the metal matrix composite, while the strengthening effects of the brittle reinforcements decrease unfavorably.

KEYWORDS: mesoscopic damage mechanisms, macroscopic properties, interphase debonding, void nucleation and growth, strengthening, ductility, parametric investigation, generalized self-consistent finite element iterative averaging method

INTRODUCTION

The damage and failure mechanisms of the metal matrix composites contain three types, namely, reinforcement fracture[1, 2], matrix-reinforcement interfacial debonding[3, 4], and ductile failure in matrix by the nucleation, growth, and coalescence of the voids from the cracking of the intermetallic inclusions and dispersoids in the matrix[5, 6]. The damage and failure mechanisms are often investigated by experimental methods, starting from metallographic observations of the strained composites. However, the numerical study by the mesomechanics of the effects of damage mechanisms on the macroscopic deformation and ductility of metal matrix composites which could not quantitatively investigated by experiments alone is also needed[7-9].

The authors, in the previous works[10, 11], developed a generalized self-consistent finite element iterative averaging method to study the strengthening mechanisms and macroscopic elastoplastic properties of metal-matrix composites, which was proved to be an effective method. In this paper, the method is united with the Gurson model for the parametric investigation of the damage mechanisms mentioned above and their relations with the macroscopic tensile properties of the SiC reinforced Al₅₄₅₆, as part of attempts for the derivation of the whole picture of damage mechanisms of metal matrix composites.

FUNDAMENTAL THEORIES OF THE CONSTITUENT DAMAGE AND THE MACROSCOPIC TENSILE PROPERTIES OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

Nucleation, Growth, and Coalescence of the Voids in Ductile Metal—the Damage and Failure of the Matrix

The yield condition for porous plastic solids in terms of a internal variable f , the void volume fraction, proposed by Gurson[12], and developed by Tvergaard[13] is of the form

$$\phi(\sigma_e, \sigma_m, \bar{\sigma}, f) = (\sigma_e/\bar{\sigma})^2 + 2fq_1 \cosh(q_2\sigma_m/2\bar{\sigma}) - 1 - q_3f^2 = 0 \quad (1)$$

where σ_e and σ_m are, respectively, macroscopic Von-Mises effective stress and hydrostatic stress acting on the voided material, while $\bar{\sigma}$ is the tensile flow strength of the matrix material. The parameters q_1 , q_2 and q_3 introduced by Tvergaard[13] are

$$q_1 = 1.5, \quad q_2 = 1, \quad q_3 = q_1^2 = 2.25 \quad (2)$$

In general, the evolution of the void volume fraction arises from the growth of existing voids and the nucleation of new voids

$$\dot{f} = (\dot{f})_{growth} + (\dot{f})_{nucleation} \quad (3)$$

Since the matrix material is plastically incompressible

$$(\dot{f})_{growth} = (1-f)G^{ij}\dot{\eta}_{ij}^p \quad (4)$$

Where $\dot{\eta}_{ij}^p$ is the plastic strain rates of the porous plastic solid, and G^{ij} is the inverse of metric tensor G_{ij} . Following Gurson[12], the rate of void nucleation controlled by plastic strain could be expressed by

$$(\dot{f})_{nucleation} = A\dot{\bar{\sigma}} \quad (5)$$

As suggested by Chu and Needleman[14], parameter A is chosen so that void nucleation follows a normal distribution. Thus, with a volume fraction of void nucleating inclusions f_N , a mean strain for nucleation ϵ_N and a standard deviation s_N

$$A = \left(\frac{1}{E_t} - \frac{1}{E} \right) \frac{f_N}{s_N \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\epsilon^p - \epsilon_N}{s_N} \right)^2 \right] \quad (6)$$

Here, E is Young's modulus, while E_t is the current tangent modulus.

Considering the coalescence effects of two neighbouring voids when the void volume fraction exceeds a critical value f_c , Tvergaard and Needleman[15] proposed

$$f^* = \begin{cases} f & f \leq f_c \\ f_c + \frac{f_u^* - f_c}{f_F - f_c} (f - f_c) & f > f_c \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $f_c=0.15$, and $f_F=0.25$. f_u^* given by $1/q_1$ is the ultimate value at which the macroscopic stress carrying capacity vanishes.

The plastic strain rates of the porous plastic solid taken in a direction normal to the flow potential satisfy

$$\dot{\eta}_{ij}^p = \lambda \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \sigma^{ij}} \quad (8)$$

By setting the plastic work rates equal to the matrix dissipation

$$(1-f)\bar{\sigma}\dot{\epsilon}^p = \sigma^{ij}\dot{\eta}_{ij}^p \quad (9)$$

the scalar multiplier, λ , in terms of the Jaumann derivative of Cauchy stress, $\hat{\sigma}^{ij}$, is determined to be

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{h} p_{ij}\hat{\sigma}^{ij} \quad (10)$$

where

$$h = - \left[(1-f) \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial f} G^{ij} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \sigma^{ij}} + \frac{E_t E}{(E - E_t)(1-f)\bar{\sigma}} \left(A \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial f} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \bar{\sigma}} \right) \sigma^{ij} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \sigma^{ij}} \right] \quad (11)$$

and

$$p_{ij} = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \sigma^{ij}} \quad (12)$$

Then, the relation between the Jaumann derivative of Cauchy stress and the Lagrangian strain increment is given in the form

$$\hat{\sigma}^{ij} = C^{ijkl} \dot{\eta}_{kl} \quad (13)$$

where

$$C^{ijkl} = L_e^{ijkl} - \frac{L_e^{ijmn} p_{mn} p_{rs} L_e^{rskl}}{h + p_{rs} L_e^{rsmn} p_{mn}} \quad (14)$$

with the elastic moduli represented by L_e^{ijkl} . In the numerical computation of finite element scheme, Eqn (13) is generally transformed into the incremental constitutive relation in terms of convected rate of Kirchhoff stress and Lagrangian strain rate [16], which is omitted here.

Fracture of Brittle Solids—the Damage and Failure of Interphase

The crack criterion for the brittle solid takes the form of maximum principal stress criterion. If σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_3 are used to represent the three principal stress, crack happens when

$$\text{Max}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3) \geq \sigma_0 \quad (15)$$

Here, σ_0 is the tensile strength of brittle solid.

Tensile Properties of Metal Matrix Composites Based on the Constituent Damage Initiation and Propagation

The generalized self-consistent finite element iterative averaging method is used in this paper to investigate the tensile properties and damage mechanisms of metal matrix composites. The detailed description of GSCFEIAM is given in [11] and will not be repeated here. The composite tensile properties with constituent damages are of the form

$$\begin{aligned} 1/E_c^{ep} = & 1/\bar{E}_m^{ep} + V_f(1/E_f - 1/\bar{E}_m^{ep})\bar{a}_f \\ & + (V_i - V_{di})(1/E_i - 1/\bar{E}_m^{ep})\bar{a}_i + V_{di}(1/E_d - 1/\bar{E}_m^{ep})\bar{a}_d \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Here, E_c^{ep} is the composite incremental tensile modulus, while \bar{E}_m^{ep} represents incremental tensile modulus of the porous matrix. E_f and E_i are Young's moduli of reinforcements and interphase, respectively. For the numerical stability in computation, the cracked parts in the interphase are regarded as a new phase with rather weak modulus E_d which is 1/10000 of E_f . V_f and V_i are, respectively, the volume fractions of reinforcements and initial interphase when no damage occurs, while V_{di} represent the volume fraction of the cracked parts in interphase evolving with the external loading. The average stress concentration factors for reinforcements and residual interphase are \bar{a}_f and \bar{a}_i , respectively, and \bar{a}_d is the average stress concentration factor of cracked parts. The incremental tensile modulus of the matrix \bar{E}_m^{ep} could be written as

$$\bar{E}_m^{ep} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{E_m} + \frac{d\bar{\epsilon}_m^p}{d\bar{\sigma}_m}} \quad (17)$$

where E_m is the Young's modulus of the matrix; while $d\bar{\sigma}_m$ and $d\bar{\epsilon}_m^p$ are, respectively; the average incremental Von-Mises effective stress and plastic strain of the matrix.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The tensile properties and mesoscopic distributions of constituent damages for SiC-Al₅₄₅₆ with interphase strength equal to 500MPa, in various loading stages, are studied within a plane strain framework. The aspect ratio and volume fraction of reinforcement are 4 and 20%, respectively. The interphase thickness adopted here is 1% of reinforcement radius. The constituent properties are: Aluminium matrix(5456): $E = 73$ GPa, $\nu = 0.33$, $\sigma_{pl} = 241$ MPa (proportional limit), $\sigma_{0.2} = 259$ MPa (0.2% offset yield), and $n = 0.01$ (work hardening exponent); SiC_w: $E = 485$ GPa, $\nu = 0.2$; Interphase: $E = 300$ GPa, $\nu = 0.25$. The void in matrix will nucleate according to the plastic strain nucleation criterion with $f_N=0.05$, $s_N=0.01$ and $\varepsilon_N=0.05$.

Stress Strain Curve of the Composite with Interphase Strength Equal to 500MPa

The composite stress-strain curve for the composite with interphase strength equal to 500MPa is shown in Fig. 1 with the curve of the circumstance without any damages in the composite as a reference. It is can be seen that the moduli of two curves are the same, because in the elastic deformation stages there is no damages in composites. While in the elastoplastic deformation stages, the composite initial work hardening rate of interphase strength 500MPa begins to decrease sharply, and the succeeding work hardening rate of this composite decreases continuously to the end of the loading stages.

The Propagation of Mesoscopic Damages of the Composite

The contours of the situations of interphase debonding and void distribution in matrix for the composite with interphase strength equal to 500MPa are shown in Fig. 2, when the external load is in the stage of 350MPa, 500MPa and 650MPa, respectively. The zones encircled by black lines represent the interphase debonding. From these contours, because of the weak interphase strength and stress concentration, the interphase debonding and voids in matrix initiate during the early loading stage, especially around the corner of reinforcement. In the mid-term loading stage, the interphase debonds completely ahead of the end of reinforcement and over half of the side wall of reinforcement. The nucleation and growth of voids develop progressively, spreading fast from the corner of reinforcement to the whole matrix. While in the latter loading stage, except the region around the corner of reinforcement a little higher and the region ahead of the reinforcement end a little lower, the distribution of void volume fractions in matrix is roughly homogeneous.

DISCUSSIONS

The interphase debonding is a rapid process, which results in the sharp decrease of the composite macroscopic work hardening rate. The interphase debonding in the region of reinforcement end will decrease the void nucleation and growth in the matrix ahead of the end of reinforcement because of the stress relaxation, while the interphase debonding in the region of reinforcement side wall will promote the void nucleation and growth in the matrix between the side wall of reinforcements, because the shear lag transfer of load will be hindered by the interphase debonding, which causes more load carried by the matrix in this region, and interphase debonding speed is nearly identical to that of the propagation of void nucleation. The void propagation and distribution in the matrix tend to be homogeneous, which are stable

well before final failure [6]. The damage is carried by the whole metal matrix. Thus, excellent composite ductility could be derived. However, the strengthening effect for the composite degrades unfavorably.

Several authors have argued that characterization of the stress-strain response for metal matrix composites in terms of 0.2% offset yield $\sigma_{0.2}$ is incomplete [11, 17, 18]. As the results show in this paper, to characterize the composite stress-strain curves in terms of $\sigma_{0.2}$, we will run risk of losing the insight of both the initial work hardening rate and succeeding ones. The characterization of composite stress-strain response should contain several parameters, for example, proportional limit, initial work hardening rate and succeeding work hardening rates which should be taken further examinations.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The situation of the interphase debonding dominates the propagation and distribution of void nucleation and growth in matrix.
2. The interphase debonding increases the composite ductility, while results in the strengthening effects of the brittle reinforcements decreasing unfavorably.
3. Characterizing the composite stress-strain curves in terms of $\sigma_{0.2}$, we will run risk of losing the insight of both the initial work hardening rate and succeeding ones.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work was supported by the Key Project of National Natural Science Foundation of China

REFERENCES

1. Lloyed, D.J., "Aspects of fracture in particulate reinforced metal matrix composites", *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 39, 1991, pp. 59-71.
2. Llorca, J., Martin, A., Ruiz, J. and Elices, M., "Particulate fracture during deformation of a spray formed metal-matrix composite", *Metall. Trans.*, Vol. 24A, 1993, pp. 1575-1588.
3. Nutt, S.R. and Duva, J.M., "A failure mechanism in Al-SiC composites", *Scripta Metall.*, Vol. 20, 1986 pp. 1055-1058.
4. Mummery, P.M., Derby, B. and Scruby, C.B., "Acoustic emission from particulate reinforced metal matrix composites", *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 41, 1993, pp. 1431-1445.
5. Kamat, S.V., Hirth, J.P. and Mehrabian, R., "Mechanical properties of particulate-reinforced Aluminum-matrix composites", *Acta Metall.*, Vol. 37, 1989, pp. 2395-2402.

6. Whitehouse, A.F. and Clyne, T.W., "Cavity formation during tensile straining of particulate and short fibre metal matrix composites", *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 41, 1993, pp. 1701-1711.
7. Tvergaard, V., "Model studies of fibre breakage and debonding in a metal reinforced by short fibres", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 41, 1993, pp. 1309-1326.
8. Llorca, J., Needleman, A. and Suresh, S., "An analysis of the effects of matrix void growth on deformation and ductility in metal-ceramic composites", *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 39, 1991, pp. 2317-2335.
9. Nutt, S.R., "Void nucleation at fibre ends in Al-SiC composites", *Scripta Metall.*, Vol. 21, 1987, pp. 705-710.
10. Chen, H.R., Su, X.F. and Williams, F.W., "The effect of imperfect interphase on overall average mechanical properties and local stress fields of multi-phase composite materials", *Composites*, Vol. 26, 1995, pp. 347-353.
11. Chen, H.R., Su, X.F. and Zheng, C.L., "Elastoplastic Behaviour of short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites", *Proceedings Tenth International Conference on Composite Materials*, Whistler, British Columbia, Canada, August 14-18, 1995, Vol. II: Metal Matrix Composites, Poursartip, A. and Street, K.N., Eds, pp1184-1190,
12. Gurson, A.L., "Continuum theory of ductile rupture by void nucleation and growth: part I-yield criteria and flow rules for porous ductile media", *J. Engng. Mater. Tech.*, Vol. 99, 1977, pp. 2-15.
13. Tvergaard, T., "Influence of voids on shear band instabilities under plane strain conditions", *Int. J. Fract.*, Vol. 17, 1981, pp. 389-407.
14. Chu, C.C. and Needleman, A., "Void nucleation effects in biaxially stretched sheets", *J. Engng. Mater. Tech.*, Vol. 102, 1980, pp. 249-256.
15. Tvergaard, T. and Needleman, A., "Analysis of the cup-cone fracture in a round tensile bar", *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 32, 1984, pp. 157-169.
16. Saje, M., Pan, J. and Needleman, A., "Void nucleation effects on shear localization in porous plastic solids", *Int. J. Fract.*, Vol. 19, 1982, pp. 163-182.
17. Christman, T., Needleman, A. and Suresh, S., "An experimental and numerical study of deformation in metal-ceramic composites", *Acta Metall.*, Vol. 37, 1989, pp. 3029-3050.
18. Levy, A. and Papazian, J.M., "Tensile properties of short fiber-reinforced SiC/Al composites: Part II. finite-element analysis", *Metall. Trans.*, Vol. 21A, 1990, pp. 411-420.

Fig. 1: The composite stress-strain curve of interphase strength, 500MPa. The circumstance without any damage in the composite is also shown as a reference.

2. (a) External load, 350MPa

2. (b) External load, 500Mpa

2. (c) External load, 650mpa

Fig. 2: Contours of interphase debonding and void distribution in the matrix, with external load in the stages of 350MPa, 500MPa and 650MPa. The zones encircled by black lines represent the interphase debonding.